

Collaborative Online Learning for Lecturers

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Abstract—This paper was prepared to see the perceptions of online lectures regarding collaborative learning, in terms of how lecturers view online collaborative learning in the higher learning institution. The purpose of this study was conducted to determine the perceptions of online lectures about collaborative learning, especially how lecturers see online collaborative learning in the university. Adult learning education enhance collaborative learning culture with the target of involving learners in the learning process to make teaching and learning more effective and open at the university. This will finally make students learning that will assist each other. It is also to cut down the pressure of loneliness and isolation might felt among adult learners. Their ways in collaborative online was also determined. In this paper, researchers collect data using questionnaires instruments. The collected data were analyzed and interpreted. By analyzing the data, researchers report the results according the proof taken from the respondents. Results from the study, it is not only dependent on the lecturer but also a student to shape a good collaborative learning practice. Rational concepts and pattern to achieve these targets be clear right from the beginning and may be good seen by a number of proposals submitted and include how the higher learning institution has trained with ongoing lectures online. Advantages of online collaborative learning show that lecturers should be trained effectively. Studies have seen that the lecturer aware of online collaborative learning. This positive attitude will encourage the higher learning institution to continue to give the knowledge and skills required.

Keywords—Collaborative Online Learning, Lecturers' Training.

I. INTRODUCTION

THIS paper wanted to evaluate the provision of lecturers for good online collaborative practice at the higher learning institution. This paper has seen the perceptions of online collaborative learning among higher learning institution lecturers, online collaborative ways and to see whether the online collaboration makes to enhance understanding. The subject matter as identified by the lecturers. This paper was conducted for the first time among a select group of trained lecturers in Kota Kinabalu. The findings are hoped to contribute to the needs of the future lecturer training program. University is an adult learning place. Online collaborative learning is one of the university learning methods: tutorial, face to face, collaboration in online learning and self-managed learning.

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II. PRACTICE OF COLLABORATIVE ONLINE LEARNING

In universities, online collaborative learning is assumed as a process in which two or more parties to assist each other in achieving the learning targets. Especially, an online collaborative learning process begins with a tutor shows the related questions and started discussions for students to discuss and reflect. By this, learners are wished to contribute further to give the views, knowledge and summaries on the question uploaded. In the mean time some students will become more active in giving to the online discussion, others may feel more relax reading the knowledge comments of their friends and explain to them, but there will also be students who seldom in making online presence. In such situations, the lecturers are hoped to motivate and guide the students to the scene [5], [7].

Studies have shown the advantages of online collaborative learning. Cezes Kecmanovic and Webb mentioned, [12] learners in distance education learning, although physically separated, they can feel belonging and sharing idea, voluntarily contribute to a team, and co-operate in overcome problems. By this, the mental build up online lecturer is vital, as positive preparation will ensure the success of online learning. In a study of nurses start distance education program, students felt that the online discussion is fitting that it will develop critical thinking among students [1]. They also mentioned that participation in online discussions make students to know their strengths and weaknesses. They like to be able to live and discuss with friends and lecturers in the whole course of the semester.

In a culture of open and separated by distance, online collaboration is suitable to help learners reach their targets fast and absorb their knowledge and experience faster. It is a method to make the students belonging to the learners community, in which the amount of knowledge they obtained to assist in the process of development of the individual. More specifically, online collaborative learning helps in recording and sorting the presence of learners. Several studies have been conducted to see the effects of collaborative teaching or learning model through distance education model [11]. In a study by Pilkington, [17] it has been said that although the presence of online tutors who are less active have a vital impact on the conversation. A few research methods have tested how the participant learners in a collaborative practice to help each other and under the aspects of the situation are reached [9], [3]. Way assist is ensured learners' involvement in the learning process, how they become self-assist and is actively committed in the learning culture. It explains the regarding virtual collaborative practice for collaborative learning. They created a tool to assess the benefits of collaborative virtual collaboration practice for the students [4].

Collaborative tools have been created based on the existing and function of collaborative tools in a virtual collaborative practice is same to a computer-to-use practice. The results show that working in a virtual collaborative practice has a potential to enhance learning where teamwork is faster than working individually, and as a whole gives a constructive learning culture.

There are six important roles to play for online lectures: a model for effective learning, track student discussions, providing expert knowledge, motivating students, providing technology support and support students in language-related issues [2]. Interactive, instructor should instruct students how to take full advantage of the strengths of each. Therefore, the cooperation of all sectors of society, it is important that the team managed to clearly teach, which may include courses outside organizational knowledge specification team members' interests, friends appreciation can give their tacit knowledge only through active question and willingness to share their personal views. Robbins and Finley [19] said that there should be the quality of online seminars to promote peer collaboration capabilities effectively to determine personal goals, to cope with the conflicting requirements to understand the views of others, and to celebrate the achievements of intent. Lecturers should be seen as a facilitator and not a very appropriate moderator presented by Cox, Clark, Heath and Plumpton [6]. They differentiate between the role of facilitators and moderators. Moderators viewed control and the power button, when teaching a unique role in student opinion, the key is to coordinate interaction.

In the mean time, Durling, Cross & Johnson [10], Mason [13], and Cox, Heath & Plumpton [6] mentioned that should be progressive online lectures encouraging students to engage in online learning. They can be asked to play the lead role as a facilitator of a topic of discussion, or summary, especially after some amount of discussion was conducted. Therefore, for the reasons above, the Open University Malaysia (OUM) has identified online collaborative learning to be an important part of the learning process. It also has to allocate at least five percent of the course evaluation will be given to students active and successful participation in online discussions [16]. This is very important, which is a good university to give lectures and students to practice collaborative learning online, to address some of these issues, including the role of perception and lecturer. Lecturers should have a positive attitude to learn new patterns and to understand the role designed for network environments. Transfer mode, through analysis and discussion on this topic, it is also very important for the practice of collaborative online learning assessment.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted among the 43 out of 90 lecturers who attended the colloquium for university lecturers in Kota Kinabalu. They were selected based on their average performance in terms of computer usage online literacy among 550 lecturers throughout Malaysia. The colloquium aims to strengthen the training session ahead of lecturers. The questionnaire was distributed to all 43 lecturers after the end

of the colloquium. 34 lecturers responded to the questionnaire. Response rate was 79%. Questionnaires have been developed in the past three research questions: (a) How online collaborative learning lecturer reacts? (b) What is the mode of online collaboration? (c) Is an online collaborative learning helps to improve understanding of the content knowledge do? The first research question is to explore the extent to which lecturers and understand the process of collaborative learning how much they agree with its effectiveness as an important part of learning at the university. Resolve how much they know what online collaboration environment project also included. Lecturers were also asked students in receiving the message sent, how often they read the message sent by the students, whether there are different types of delivery. The second research question was designed to determine the pattern of online collaboration, active students is how to be sent a message to the group, how they respond positively to the delivery of their friends and judgment has been issued. The third research question insight into how lecturers to ensure that their collaborative learning, to promote students' knowledge content.

IV. PILOT STUDIES

According to Polit et.al, [18] a pilot study refers to a small study or trial version done in preparation for a larger study or major. De Vaus [8] states that the purpose of the pilot study was to test the reliability and validity of the survey questionnaire and to reduce errors in the actual study. Advantages of conducting a pilot study are to help researchers obtain early indicator of any part of the study may not be accurate or fail. It also could help researchers identify any rules or instruments of incorrect or inaccurate [3]. According to Najib, [15] an instrument is valid can trust and if the Cronbach's alpha exceed 0.6. The three parts of the questionnaire Cronbach's alpha has reached more than 0.6, then the research instrument has high reliability and can be used in the actual study.

In this study, a pilot study was not done because the questionnaire that researchers wanted to test a pilot study was confirmed. This is due to the questions and questionnaires be adopted based on previous studies by Zoraini Wati Abas and Abtar Kaur's writing titled "Preparing Tutors for Online Collaborative Learning at the Open University Malaysia" [20]. Previous research questions have been tested and certified reliability. Thus, for this study, questionnaires form is taken and modified from Zoraini Wati Abas and Abtar Kaur's writing titled "Preparing Tutors for Online Collaborative Learning at the Open University Malaysia" and Mitra Education study entitled "Collaborative Learning Questionnaire" [14].

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION: HOW ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING LECTURER REACTS?

The report found that online collaborative learning on the basis of lecturers (Table I). When the instructor asked if they understand the process of cooperative learning, lecturers,

namely 95.6% agreed or strongly agreed to the statement. Only 5.9% of the lecturers said that they do not understand the process. Lecturers believe that online collaborative learning is an important part of university teaching, the majority (96.6%) of the lecturers in this group reacted. Only one case (2.9%) did not agree lecturer. When asked if they know what is expected of them in an online collaborative environment, 12 (35.3%) of the respondents strongly agreed and 21 (61.8%) of respondents said that they know what is expected of them, in an online collaborative environment. Only 2 (2.9%) of the respondents said they did not know what to expect from them. 75.8% of lecturers in reading frequency transmission, the report said, they saw three or more times a week delivery. 78.7% agreed or strongly agreed that there is a variety of delivery. A total of 33 lecturers statement said, "I understand the transmission of information in the discussion board", lecturer 28 (84.9%) had a positive response and 5 (15.1%) than negative feedback statement.

The results showed that active lecturer in online collaborative learning. They believe that online collaborative learning is very important. 75.8% of lecturers in line to see the delivery of more than three times a week. Most (84.9%) of the lecturers who are online collaborative learning helps the quality of learning. These findings may be largely due to the fact that the university has a very strict culture, and committed to train instructors began working as a lecturer in the line. University lecturer described the concept of e-learning aspects of the seminar online, process and benefits of online facilities and the role of online lectures and diverse. In addition, they have a hand session at the University learning management system, in particular how to use it. In addition, each offers special lectures to provide an effective online teaching, therefore, recommended teacher training system has not changed, but the latest features to enhance the technical how to be an effective collaborative learning online.

Taking into account this fact, online collaborative learning is relatively new, some of the lecturers, proposed the establishment of ongoing online discussion groups, and how to develop effective learning environments online as part of the ongoing training cooperation. Topics may include all aspects of the Internet, the role of online facilitators and skills, effective guidance to build a learning community. Some models can be selected online forum to promote discussion of a new university lecturer. Moderator model can provide guidance and incentives to encourage students to actively participate, participants from passive submission, a useful resource, and in the process, help develop the skills of effective online. Discussions and networking are also included to show how it can be done. Are right skills to do their own online lecturers and students. Moderator model can be used as a support group for new lecturers, as they develop or improve their skills.

TABLE I
 ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING LECTURER'S REACTION

Items	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)
1. I understand the process of collaborative learning (n = 34)	0 (0)	2 (5.9)	20 (58.8)	12 (35.3)
2. Online collaborative learning is an important component of learning at university (n = 34)	0 (0)	1 (2.9)	19 (55.9)	14 (41.2)
3. I know what is expected of me on the environment of online collaborative learning (n = 34)	0 (0)	1 (2.9)	21 (61.8)	12 (35.3)
4. I understand posting message in discussion board (n = 33)	1 (3.0)	4 (12.1)	19 (57.6)	9 (27.3)
5. I read the message delivery three times or more per week (n = 32)	1 (3.1)	6 (18.8)	16 (50.0)	9 (28.1)
6. There are a variety of writing the message delivery (n = 33)	2 (6.1)	5 (15.2)	18 (54.5)	8 (24.2)

VI. WHAT IS THE MODE OF COLLABORATIVE ONLINE?

Students rely on online lectures (see Table II). It can be inferred from the frequency of delivery to their friends and their lecturer's delivery problems. Most people, 66.6% of the lecturers, the students do not send a message to the group. 61.7% of the lecturers, the students in answering questions from their peers who are not active. In contrast, the majority of students and lecturers are teaching childbirth questions. Most students still rely on lecturer in online collaborative learning environments. By promoting effective discussion between the student lecturers, eventually replaced with faith, respect their colleagues learned counsel. It is believed that this is an assimilation process that requires time and patience. Through effective training, it is also expected in the near future, the emergence of a new culture of learning and development. This can be determined by the University, can be seen in policies to promote effective learning online. In addition, it seems that students are still very dependent on the support of online lectures. Employees in any organization's ability to lifelong learning is essential for survival, it may be timely to remind students that are not too dependent on personal development experts. In addition, it may happen that the lecturers may not be willing to relinquish their power. Lecturers have to disclose the fact that he and the students in this process, rather than a separate abuse and control. Therefore, during the training emphasis should take into account these aspects should be discussed in detail and case studies. Two-pronged strategy will be incorporated into training courses future lecturers and students.

TABLE II
MODE OF ONLINE COLLABORATION

Items	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)
1. I noticed that most of the students are active in sending questions to the group. (n = 33)	5 (15.1)	17 (51.5)	9 (27.3)	2 (6.1)
2. I noticed that all the students are active in answering questions from the delivery of their friends. (n = 34)	6 (17.6)	15 (44.1)	11 (32.4)	2 (5.9)
3. Most of the questions sending directed to the lecturer. (n = 31)	1 (3.2)	10 (32.3)	17 (54.8)	3 (9.7)

VII. IS ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING HELPS TO IMPROVE UNDERSTANDING OF THE CONTENT KNOWLEDGE DOING?

Most teachers believe that online collaborative learning helps to increase the content knowledge. Table III shows that 80.8 % of the lecturers that the online collaborative learning increases knowledge. Most of the lecturers said that 90.9 % of students who reflect the issues rose in the discussion before answering delivered. Most of the lecturers (72.7%) also saw that they have an adjustable focus on specific issues. Overall, 65.6% of lecturers believe that the discussion is interactive. However, only 52.9 % of lecturers and students understand them. Instructors provide feedback, students tend to ask questions lecturer exchange. This is necessary to determine whether the issues discussed on certain issues, but also reflects the answers given. Further studies should be conducted. It also determines the actual quality of the content provided by the interaction of knowledge increases. This study aims to extend the students.

TABLE III
LECTURERS' VIEW OF ONLINE COLLABORATIVE LEARNING HELP TO IMPROVE UNDERSTANDING OF THE CONTENT KNOWLEDGE DOES

Items	Strongly Disagree n(%)	Disagree n(%)	Agree n(%)	Strongly Agree n(%)
1. Improved knowledge content in online collaborative learning (n = 31)	1 (3.2)	5 (16.1)	22 (71.0)	3 (9.7)
2. I think about the questions raised in the discussion before offering answers (n = 33)	0 (0)	3 (9.1)	20 (60.6)	10 (30.3)
3. Well-moderated online discussions and focus on specific issues (n = 33)	1 (3.0)	8 (24.3)	21 (63.6)	3 (9.1)
4. Online discussion is interactive (n = 32)	1 (3.1)	10 (31.0)	16 (50.0)	5 (15.6)
5. Students contribute to sudden understanding of each other (n= 34)	2 (5.9%)	14 (41.2)	15 (44.1)	3 (8.8)

VIII. CONCLUSION

Establishing effective learning practice cooperation for full time courses in University indeed depends on the lecturers and students. Concepts and methods to achieve this target which started by OUM are exactly rational. The result of this study in

is in line with the previous study done by Zoraini and Abtar and their findings. Finally, Lecturers should be trained periodically to get the knowledge and skills required.

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